

**A DRUG REVIEW ON SIDDHA HERBO-MINERAL FORMULATION GUNMA KUDORI
MEZHUGU FOR DHOORA SOOLAI W. S.R TO (DYSMENORRHOEA)**

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ABSTRACT

Siddha system of medicine uses herbal and herbo-mineral formulations in therapeutics since immemorial. The phytochemical and pharmacological activity of Siddha herbo-mineral formulation Gunma kudori mezhugu being used for soolai diseases especially for Dhoora soolai. (Dysmenorrhoea). It is a pathological condition described in Siddha medicine, primarily related to menstrual disorders in females. It refers to painful menstruation of sufficient magnitude so as to incapacitate day to day activities, often accompanied by symptoms such as lower abdominal pain, discomfort and systemic disturbances like nausea, vomiting, fatigue, diarrhoea, headache, tachycardia. Primary dysmenorrhea is associated with increase in prostaglandins (PGF_{2α} & PGE₂). While secondary dysmenorrhea is associated with underlying pelvic conditions such as endometriosis, adenomyosis and fibroids. In Siddha the condition is understood as vitiation if vatham, maelnokkukaal and keezhnokkukaal leading to blockage of the reproductive channels. The present review was carried to describe different activities of each ingredient of Gunma kudori mezhugu. It is one of the safe and efficacious medicines used traditionally for the treatment of Dhoora soolai. The review describes various facts like active constituents, pharmacological actions of the individual ingredients. The pharmacological common activity of Gunma kudori mezhugu showed anti-spasmodic, anti-inflammatory, anti-emetic activity.

KEYWORDS: Siddha, Gunma kudori mezhugu, Dhoora soolai, Dysmenorrhea.

INTRODUCTION

Siddha is a holistic system of medicine developed by enlightened sages known as Siddhars who combined their knowledge of nature, the human body and spiritual insight to promote health and longevity. W.H.O recommends herbal based traditional remedies because of their safety easy availability, low treatment cost for the diseases. Dhoorasoolai means painful menstruation (Dysmenorrhoea). It is one of the most common gynecological concerns among all menstruating, regardless of age or race. The prevalence varies from

16% and 91% in reproductive age group. And severe pain observed in 2% to 21% of the individual. According to siddha system of medicines the diseases are classified in to 4448 in numbers. Siddha system categorizes soolai diseases in to 15 types Dhoorasoolai is among the soolai diseases than can be correlated with Dysmenorrhoea which is explained in Siddha literature mentioned in Siddha Yugi Vaidhya Chinthamani. Gunma kudori mezhugu a herbo-mineral formulation is indicated for Dhoora soolai mentioned in Noikaluku Siddha Parikaram classical literature.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

HERBAL INGREDIENTS OF GUNMA KUDORI MEZHUGU

S.NO	PLANTS	BOTANICAL NAME	FAMILY	PARTS USED	DOSE
1	Sukku	Zingiber officinale	Zingiberaceae	Dried rhizome	35gms
2	Mizhagu	Piper nigrum	Piperaceae	Fruit	35gms
3	Thippli	Piper longum	Piperaceae	Fruit	35gms
4	Omam	Trachyspermum ammi	Apiaceae	Fruit	35gms
5	Kirampu	Syzygium aromaticum	Myrtaceae	Flower	35gms

6	Modi ver	Piper longum	Piperaceae	Fruit	35gms
7	Kostam	Costus speciosus	Costaceae	Rhizome	35gms
8	Perungayam	Ferula asafoetida	Apiaceae	Resin	35gms
9	Poondu	Allium sativum	Alliaceae	Bulb	175gms
10	Panai vellam	Borassus flabellifer	Arecaceae	Sap	175gms
11	Thaen/Honey	-	-	-	175gms

MINERAL INGREDIENTS OF GUNMA KUDORI MEZHUGU:

S.NO	MINERALS	ENGLISH NAME	CHEMICAL NAME	DOSE
1	Induppu	Rock salt	Sodium chloride	35gms
2	Kaluppu	Sochal salt	Sodium chloride	35gms
3	Chothuppu	Common salt	Sodium chloride	35gms
4	Appalakaram	Baking soda	Sodium carbonate	35gms
5	Valayaluppu	Medicinal salt/Bangle salt	Sodium chloride	35gms
6	Venkaram	Borax	Sodium baborate	35gms
7	Navacharam	Sal Ammoniac	Ammonium chloride	35gms
8	Vediuppu	Salt Petre	Potassium nitrate	35gms

METHOD OF PREPARATION

Take weighed amount of borax and fried in a clean earthen vessel for purification. Then fry all the above mentioned herbal ingredients except poondu, panai vellam, honey. After frying grind it in mixer still it becomes fine powder. Then the obtained powder is filtered through sieve. After proper sieving poondu is added in mortar and pestle and grinded it into a fine paste

then the powdered ingredients and the above mentioned salts are added little by little till the drugs are properly mixed with fine paste then add panai vellam, honey and grinded until it reaches semisolid consistency and collected in a clean glass jar.

DOSAGE

Sundai alavu (1-2gms), Twice a day, after food.

S.NO	Botanical name/Chemical name	Phytochemical/Chemical constituents	Pharmacological activity
1	Zingiber officinale	Zingiberol, Zingiberine, Sesquiterpenes, Bisapolene, Zingerols	Carminative, Analgesic, Antibacterial, Antispasmodic, Stomachic, Laxative, Vasodilator, prostoglandin inhibitor.
2	Piper nigrum	Chavicine, piperine, piperidine, piperetine, piperamine, piperamide.	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, prostoglandin inhibitor, Antimicrobial, Carminative, Antispasmodic, Antifungal.
3	Piper longum	Piperine, Piperitine, Brachystamide, Asarine, Pipericide, Piper longumine.	Anti-inflammatory, Antibacterial, Antifungal.
4	Trachyspermum ammi	Thymol, Carvacrol, Para-cymene, Myrcene, Caphene, Carvone, limonene,	Antispasmodic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, analgesic, antioxidant, antihistamine.
5	Syzygium aromaticum	Eugenol, Beta-caryophyllene, Kaempferol, Eugenin, Stigmasterol, Campesterol	Antinociceptive, Antibacterial, Antifungal, Analgesic, Anti-inflammatory, Anesthetic, Antispasmodic.
6	Piper longum	Piperine, Piperitine, Brachystamide, Asarine, Pipericide, Piper longumine.	Analgesic, Antibacterial, Antifungal.
7	Costus speciosus	Costunolide, Diosgenin, Lupeol, Santamarine, Eremanthin,	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, Stomachic.
8	Ferula asafoetida	Luteolin, Chrysoeriol 7-O-glucoside, Quercetin 3-O-Glucoside, 3,5-Di-O-Caffeoylquinic acid, Limonene.	Antifungal, Emmenagogue, Antioxidative, Anti-inflammatory, Antispasmodic, Carminative, prostoglandin inhibitor.
9	Allium sativum	Allicin, Alliin, Quercetin, E-Ajoene,	Anti-inflammatory, Antispasmodic, Antifungal, Antioxidant, Carminative.
10	Borassus flabellifer (Palm candy)	Ascorbic acid, Nicotinic acid, Riboflavin, Zinc, Potassium, Iron, Glutamic acid	Diuretic, Anti-flatulent.
11	Sodium chloride (Rock salt)	Sodium, Calcium, Chloride, Magnesium	Anti-flatulent, Carminative, Stomachic, Diuretic.
12	Sodium chloride (Sochal salt)	Sodium, Calcium, Chloride.	Digestive, carminative, Laxative, Anti-

			Flatulent.
13	Sodium chloride (Common salt)	Sodium, Chloride.	Emetic, Stomachic, Anti-pyretic.
14	Sodium carbonate (Baking soda)	Sodium, Carbonate.	Carminative, Anti-Flatulent, Antacid.
15	Sodium chloride (Medicinal salt)	Sodium, Chloride.	Carminative, Digestive, Laxative, Antacid, Antiseptic.
16	Sodium baborate (Borax)	Sodium, Boron, Oxygen.	Emmenggogue, Anti-septic, Astringent, Diuretic, Antidote.
17	Ammonium chloride (Sal Ammoniac)	Ammonium, Chloride, Nitrogen, Hydrogen, Chlorine.	Expectorant, Antacid, Diaphoretic stimulant.
18	Potassium nitrate (Salt Petre)	Potassium, Nitrogen, Oxygen.	Diaphoretic, Diuretic, Coolant.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Siddha system of medicine is being practiced by a large population in South India. Gunma Kudori Mezhugu, a classical Siddha formulation, has been traditionally indicated for Gynecological ailments including Dhoola Soolai (Dysmenorrhea). In Siddha literature, Dhoola Soolai is described as severe abdominal and pelvic pain radiating to the back and thighs during menstruation, often associated with dearrangement of Vatham, maelnökkukaal and keezhnökkukaal leading to blockage of the reproductive channels. From the review of Siddha literature, it is evident that Gunma Kudori Mezhugu is effective in the management of Dhoola Soolai (Dysmenorrhea). The development of Siddha medicine with perspectives of safety, efficacy and quality will help to preserve the traditional system of medicine and also the use of natural products in the health care. Plants & minerals serve vast source for varied phytoconstituents exhibiting pharmacological property. The ingredients of Gunma Kudori Mezhugu having antispasmodic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, stomachic, antacid, anesthetic. This activity finding demonstrates that Gunma kudori mezhugu drastically reduce the spasmodic pain, nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, headache. The drug *Ferula asafoetida* is extensively studied for its pharmacological activities of Antifungal, Emmenggogue, Antioxidative, Anti-inflammatory, Antispasmodic, Carminative, prostoglandin inhibitor. The resin of the plant is used to treat stomachache, colic pain and chronic gynecological disorders. *Zingiber officinale*, *Piper nigrum*, *Piper longum*, *Trachyspermum ammi*, *Allium sativum* possess anti-spasmodic, immune modulator effect which helps to regulate immune system. *Zingiber officinalis* has Carminative, Analgesic, Antibacterial, Antispasmodic, Stomachic, Laxative, Vasodilator, prostoglandin inhibitor and helps to prevent from lower abdominal pain. *Piper nigrum* has Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, prostaglandin inhibitor, Antimicrobial, Carminative. Antispasmodic, Antifungal. *Piper longum* has analgesic effect helps to prevent from abdominal pain. Sodium baborate has Emmenggogue, Anti-septic, Astringent, Diuretic, Antidote effect helps to prevent infections like cervicitis. Our finding suggest that Siddha herbal preparations have great potential as antispasmodic, anti-inflammatory, prostanglandin inhibitor, carminative activity these plants reported to be used in the treatment of gynecological disorders. Our findings suggest that, Siddha herbal preparations have great potential as antispasmodic, prostoglandin inhibitor,

analgesic effect thus can be used for the treatment of dhoorasoolai.

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